

A STUDY TO ASSESS THE EFFECTIVENESS OF VIDEO ASSISTED TEACHING ON KNOWLEDGE REGARDING FIRST AID MANAGEMENT OF SCHOOL STUDENTS AMONG NURSERY AND PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS AT SELECTED SCHOOLS IN BAHOUR, PUDUCHERRY.

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Abstract

Background:

Children are prone to injuries due to their active nature and lack of awareness, making schools a common place for accidents like falls, epistaxis, foreign body insertions, and bites. In most cases, timely first aid can prevent complications. However, many primary school teachers lack adequate first aid knowledge. In India, limited training and resources make it challenging to manage such situations effectively.

Aim:

The main aim of the present study was to assess the effectiveness of video assisted teaching on knowledge regarding first aid management of school students among nursery and primary school teachers at selected school.

Methods:

A Quasi experimental one-group pre-test post-test design was used among 48 primary school teachers. A self structured questionnaire measured knowledge before and after a 45-minute teaching session. Data analysis included descriptive statistics and paired t-test.

Results:

The finding revealed pre-test knowledge levels were inadequate 8 (16.7%), moderate 37 (77.1%), and adequate 3 (6.2%). Post-test: 100% demonstrated adequate knowledge. the post test result shows that,there is significant increase in level of knowledge regarding first aid management of school students Among nursery and primary school teachers. The increase in knowledge scores was statistically significant $t=16.455$, $p=0.0057$

Conclusion:

Effectiveness of video assisted teaching helps to improve a teachers knowledge

KEY WORDS:

Children, Planned Teaching Programme, Safety, First Aid Measures, Knowledge, Emergency Conditions, School Teachers.

I INTRODUCTION**1.1 Background**

Children are prone to injuries due to their active nature and lack of awareness, making schools a common place for accidents like falls, epistaxis, foreign body insertions, and bites. In most cases, timely first aid can prevent complications. However, many primary school teachers lack adequate first aid knowledge. In India, limited training and resources make it challenging to manage such situations effectively.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

EFFECTIVENESS OF VIDEO ASSISTED TEACHING ON KNOWLEDGE REGARDING FIRST AID MANAGEMENT OF SCHOOL STUDENTS AMONG NURSERY AND PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS AT SELECTED SCHOOLS IN BAHOUR, PUDUCHERRY.

1.3 Objectives

- To assess the pretest and post test level of Knowledge on First aid management of School Students among Nursery and Primary school teachers .

- To evaluate the effectiveness of Video assisted teaching Programme on Knowledge on First aid management of School Students.
- To associate the Pretest level of Knowledge on First aid management of School Students among Nursery and Primary school teachers knowledge on First aid management of school students among nursery And primary school teachers.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Gowri and Missiriya,et.al.(2018) conducted a across-sectional study was assessing the knowledge and practice of school teachers towards health of school children. Cross-sectional survey conducted among school teachers in Chennai, Thiruvellore and Kancheepuram. Structured questionnaire was used and 900 teachers were randomly selected from schools and assessed on their knowledge and practice regarding health of children. Totally 78% of the teachers were not having adequate knowledge and 89% were not having the practice of maintaining health care of school children.

Rohitash Kumar et.al, (2018) conducted a study was to assess the knowledge of primary school teachers regarding first aid management of minor accidents among children (5-10 Years) at selected primary schools of Ambala district Haryana. Descriptive research design was used. the total 40 e primary school teachers.the study taken by convenient sampling technique. . The data was collected from teachers over The results show that most of the primary school teachers (52.5%) had moderate knowledge score (16-21), followed by 37.5 percent teachers who had excellent knowledge score (21-27), a small portion (10%) of schoolteachers had poor knowledge.

3. Methodology

3.1 Design

- **Type:** quasi-experimental one-group pre-test and post-test design.
- **Setting:** selected Schools in Bahour, Puducherry.

3.2 Participants

- **Sample:** 48, primary school teachers, (Random sampling).
- **Inclusion Criteria:**
 - ◆ The Nursery and primary school teachers.
 - ◆ Teachers who are willing to participate.

3.3 Instrument

- **Tools:**
SECTION A: Demographic Variables,
SECTION B: self-structured knowledge questionnaires (20items)
- **Scoring:** Inadequate (<10), moderate (10-20), adequate (>20).

3.4 Analysis:

- Descriptive statistics (mean, SD, SPSS v28)
- Inferential (paired t-test, chi-square).
- KW=12.5688

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of objective video assisted teaching programme for schoolteachers in bahour, Puducherry. A total of 48 primary school teachers in this study after providing oral consent and receiving an explanation regarding the purpose and procedures of data collection. Data was gathered using a self-structured questionnaire.

- **Assess the pretest and posttest level of Knowledge on First aid management of School Students among Nursery and Primary school teachers ..**

The first objective was to determine the knowledge among primary school teachers .The overall score in pretest knowledge of teachers showed that 16.7% of teachers had inadequate knowledge, 77.1.% of teachers had average knowledge and 6.2% of teachers had adequate knowledge.

Frequency and percentage distribution of first aid management among nursery and Primary Schools

(N = 48)

LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE	Pre test		Post test	
	No of teachers(n)	Percentage (%)	No of teachers(n)	Percentage (%)
Inadequate knowledge	8	16.7%	0	0.0%
Moderate knowledge	37	77.1%	6	12.5%
Adequate knowledge	3	6.2%	42	87.5%
Total	48	100.0%	48	100.0%

- Evaluate the effectiveness of Video assisted teaching Programme on Knowledge on First aid management of School Students

Mean and Standard deviation of knowledge level among nursery and primary school teachers in Experimental group

The Second objective was to determine Mean and standard deviation of first aid management among nursery and primary school teachers .In experimental group regarding the mean and standard deviation among teachers with first aid management during pretest was 11.50 and mean standard deviation among teachers with first aid management during posttest was 17.23 respectively The calculated Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test value was $t=16.455$ at $p<0.001$ which was not significant Regarding the experimental group the mean and standard deviation among teachers with first aid management during pretest was 11.50 and the mean standard deviation among teachers with first aid management during posttest was 17.23 respectively.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Paired Differences	Paired t-test	p-value
Pre test	48	11.50	2.39	0.35	5.729	16.455	<0.001
Post test	48	17.23	2.37	0.34			

$P<0.001$ -HSS (highly statistically significance) ***

		N	Mean	SD	Median	MW/K W test	P value
Family Income	Below Rs 10,000	12	11.92	2.19	12	12.5688	0.0057
Family Income	Rs. 10,000-20,000	14	9.86	2.18	10.5	12.5688	0.0057
	Rs.20,000-30,000	8	11.25	1.67	11		
	Above Rs 30,000	14	12.93	2.23	13		

Association between the pretest level of knowledge on first aid management among nursery and primary school teachers and their selected demographic variables.

The Third objective was to determine Association between the knowledge level of nursery and primary school teacher first aid management and selected demographic variable with regards to demographic variable Family income had significant associated video assisted teaching regarding first aid management KW=12.5688 p=0.0057 respectively. Hence the stated hypothesis is H2 there is significance association between pretest level of knowledge regarding first aid management among nursery and primary school teachers with their selected demographic variable was accepted.

The remaining demographic variables were Age, Gender, Education, Family Income, Religion, Residence, School, Experience, Marital status, Had training, Given first-aid did not have any significant association with video assisted teaching regarding first aid management hence the stated hypothesis No significance between pretest level of knowledge regarding first aid management among Nursery and primary school teachers with selected their selected demographic variables hence the stated hypothesis is H2 there is significance

association between pre test level of knowledge regarding first aid management among nursery and primary school teachers with their selected demographic variable was rejected.

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

SUMMARY

The present study was to assess the effectiveness of video assisted teaching on knowledge regarding first aid management of school students among nursery and primary school teachers at selected schools in Bahour, Puducherry.

IMPLICATION

The findings of the study implied in the area of nursing education and nursing administration, nursing research and nursing services.

IMPLICATIONS TO NURSING ADMINISTRATION

Nurse can plan, organize, and conduct the health awareness on prevention of child sexual abuse.

IMPLICATIONS TO NURSING EDUCATION

The nursing educator must be able to assisted teaching on knowledge on first aid management of school students Among nursery and primary school teachers at Selected school in Bahour, Puducherry”

LIMITATIONS

- Sample size that was limited to 48 teachers.
- Period of study that limited to six days.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- This study can be replicated on a Small sample size and also in different settings.
- This study can be conducted among graduate teachers.
- This study can be conducted by including a lesser number of samples

CONCLUSION

The main aim of the present study was to assess the effectiveness of video assisted teaching on knowledge regarding first aid management of school students among nursery and primary school teachers at selected schools. The samples were only in experimental groups. The mean value of pretest was 11.50 and mean value of posttest was 17.23. And the standard deviation of pretest was 2.39 were as the standard deviation of posttest was 2.37. The study revealed, inadequate knowledge - 0(0,0%), moderate level knowledge- (12.5%), adequate level knowledge – (87.5%). Hence studying is **effective**.

REFERENCES:

1. Gajenda. Impact of health education on preventive practices & Journal of Nursing and Health Science.2015;4 (1)
2. B.Muneeswari. Global Journal of Medicine and Public Health. 2014
3. Dwivedi, Samantha N. Journal of Paediatrics and Neonatology 2008; 8 (1).
4. Singh Aprajita, Ghoshdhruv et al. Journal of Indian Association of Paediatric Surgeons.2010
5. Jyothi Lakshmi. first aid measures for foreign body aspiration in primary school children on knowledge among TTC students European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical
6. K Mathew stella, S Seema. Knowledge first aid management regarding foreign body aspiration among underfive community Global Journal for Research Analysis. 2015
- 7.Meena Pandi. Effectiveness of video assisted teaching on knowledge regarding prevention of home accidents among t under-five children Child Health Nursing. 2016.
8. Samant K. First aid emergency.Vora Medical Publications; New Delhi 2010
9. St. John's First aid to the injured.St. John's publications. New York: 2013.
10. Shobhamasih,Princy john L. Management of Immediate Injuries. Nursing Journal of India. 201